

CFD Analysis of an Open Volumetric Air Receiver and Comparison with 10 kW_{th} Solar Tests

Context:

ASTERIX-CAESAR proposes a hybrid power plant consisting of a **power tower system** based on an open volumetric receiver and **compressed air energy storage**. The primary heat transfer fluid is air and the open volumetric receiver is made of **SiC ceramic foam**.

Aim of Pilot Plant:

- New operating strategy for power tower plants
- **Efficient & accessible materials for low operation cost** 1
- Explore potential applications of residual heat

→→ CSP to an accessible and cost-effective option

L. Alonso-Pardo¹, D. Sanchez-Señoran¹, M. Biencinto¹, J. Fernandez¹, F. Zaversky², X. Randez², A. Fuessel³, W. Pritzkow⁴, A. Avila-Marin¹

¹ CIEMAT – Plataforma Solar de Almería (PSA), Tabernas, Almería, Spain.
² CENER – Solar Energy & Storage, Sarriguren, Pamplona, Spain.
³ Fraunhofer Institute for Ceramic Technologies and Systems IKTS, Dresden, Germany.
⁴ Walter E.C. Pritzkow Spezialkeramik, Filderstadt, Germany

Aim of study:

For optimal operation & yield of the plant, the properties of absorber, cup, and geometry of the **receiver** are studied in this work to increase the efficiency of this crucial component.

- Optimization of thermal efficiency → **improves 1**
- Validation of 3D CFD model → **For potential use in a simulation of the full receiver.**
- Characterization of thermal & fluid dynamic effective properties of component → **for implementation in full plant model**
- + Comparison of proposed materials – Proprietary ceramic production recipe and design.

Methodology:

Operation & Simulation Conditions:

Absorber Outlet Temp. & corresponding mFR	Solar furnace shutter aperture & Corresponding Solar Heat Flux		
600 °C	20 %	25 %	30 % Shutter
11-19 g/s	5.2 kW _{th}	7.1 kW _{th}	8.8 kW _{th}

x 7 Foam Samples

Experimental:

- Operation conditions:
 - Mass Flow Rate (mFR) adjusted with blower
 - Incident Flux adjusted with shutter
- Resulting measures for abs. module heat flux:
 - air temperature (thermocouples)
 - mFR (heat exchanger)

Numerical:

- RANS
- Quasi-Static
- Homogenous model
- LTNE

Experimental setup: Solar furnace bench test

3D CAD+CFD Model:

Boundary conditions:

- mFR
- Flux Map
- Ref. Pressure
- Ref. Amb temp
- Material properties (foam and cup)

Fluid Cross sections, transverse

Results:

Flux Map at the Absorber Inlet:

Air temp at the Absorber Outlet:

- Comparison between experimental and numerical values air temperature at the cup outlet.
- Question: **Are the numerical values within the range of experimental data?**

Summary of the CFD Model:

- ▶ Simulation valid for:
 - ▶ Porosity 84% - 89%
 - ▶ mFR 13.4 g/s - 28.5 g/s
 - ▶ Flux 5.0 kW_{th} - 9.0 kW_{th}
- ▶ Capabilities of model:
 - ▶ 2D Flux map implementation
 - ▶ 3D fluid thermal and dynamic development
 - ▶ Heat Flux calculation → Future works: Thermal efficiency calc.
 - ▶ Pressure drop → Future works: Blower Energy consumption calc.

Conclusions/Outlook :

- A 3D CFD numerical model for 5-9 kW_{th} conditions was built and validated.
- According to the model, for 600 °C at the absorber outlet, A-2 and B-3 have the **best thermal efficiencies** for each recipe type, those being 86.3% and 86.7% respectively, both for 7 kW_{th}.
- New tests of best absorbers will be done on further outlet air temperature operation conditions.